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Cover Photo: Holotype of *Telchinia issoria* (Credit: Peter Smetacek)

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NEW ALTITUDE RANGE OF *CLELEA DISCRIMINIS* SWINHOE, 1891 (LEPIDOPTERA: ZYGAENIDAE) IN ASSAM, INDIA

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ABSTRACT

The current observation extends the known distributional range of the genus *Clelea* Walker, 1854 to Assam, India, and records a new low altitudinal range for *C. discriminis*.

KEYWORDS *Clelea discriminis*, New altitudinal range, New Record, Garbhanga Reserve Forest, Assam

INTRODUCTION

The Northeast region of India is a diverse and captivating area that encompasses the Eastern Himalayas, the rugged Northeast hills comprising the Patkai-Naga Hills and Lushai Hills, as well as the vast plains of the Brahmaputra and Barak Valley (Chatterjee *et al.*, 2006). Among its remarkable features, Assam stands out as one of the most extraordinary biodiversity zones in the world. This distinction can be attributed to Assam's strategic location within the transitional zone that merges the Indian, Indo-Malayan, and Indo-Chinese bio-geographical regions. In Assam, a total

of 1,365 species of moths have been recorded (Joshi *et al.*, 2021) and many more to come. Recently, *Padenia acutifascia* de Joannis, 1928 was reported from Assam (Thapa, 2021) and *Clanis hyperion bhutana* Brechlin, 2014 was reported from Dimapur, Nagaland (Thapa *et al.*, 2022), which borders Assam.

Clelea discriminis Swinhoe, 1891

The genus *Clelea* Walker, 1854 consists of 8 species, which are found in the northeastern region of India (Joshi *et al.*, 2021). *Clelea discriminis* and *C. sapphirina* Walker, 1854 are nearly identical in appearance, but *discriminis* differs from *sapphirina* in the streaks from the base of the fore wing being green, and the lower one being along the median nervure; the subapical markings more parallel; the marginal line and blue on hind wing absent (Hampson, 1892).

Distribution: Sikkim; Naga Hills, 3000 feet (Hampson 1892); Meghalaya; Nagaland (Joshi *et al.*, 2021)

RESULT

On May 14, 2023, at 11:32 hr, three individuals of *C. discriminis* were observed in Garbhanga Reserve Forest, Kamrup, Assam. The specimens were resting on leaves near a stream within a dense forest habitat. The present record confirms its presence in Assam. Previous records of *C. discriminis* indicated its presence at an altitude of 914 m (3000 feet). However, this paper reports the species at altitudes ranging from 80 m (244 feet) to 670 m (2042 feet) above mean sea level.

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Figure: *Clelea discriminis* from Garbhanga Reserve Forest